

Kuy traditional religions

also known as “Khamen-Boran, Kui, Kuy, Kuay, Kuoy, Soai, Soei, Suay, Suei, Sui, and Suoi”

Secondary source

Entered by Sarah-Kim Holma, University of Leiden

*Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

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Kuy is an ethnonym used for people who speak the Kuy language, which is from the Katuic group of the Austroasiatic family. The Kuy are known by different names across Thailand, Laos and Cambodia. Note that today there is ambiguity regarding how Kuy self-identify, which makes it difficult to define or measure their cultural practices with complete accuracy. The following map includes areas where traditional Kuy communities live.

Date Range: 1000 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Kuy-language speakers in mainland Southeast Asia

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia

This is a general estimate of the extent of Kuy language speakers (credit: Mann and Markowski 2005)

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mann, Noel, and Linda Markowski. “A Rapid Appraisal of Kuy Dialects Spoken in Cambodia.” SIL Electronic Reports 2005-018. Retrieved 18 May 2013, from Website: SIL International, SIL Electronic Survey Reports 2005-018, 2005, www.sil.org/resources/archives/9014.
- Source 2: Swift, Peter. “Changing Ethnic Identities among the Kuy in Cambodia: Assimilation, Reassertion and the Making of Indigenous Identity.” *Asia Pacific Viewpoint*, vol. 54, no. 3, 2013, pp. 296–308.
- Source 3: Sidwell, Paul, and Kees Jan Bos. “Kui Ntua.” *The Handbook of Austroasiatic Languages (2 Vols)*, edited by Mathias Jenny and Paul Sidwell, Brill, 2015, pp. 837–880.
- Source 1: “The Katuic Branch.” SEALANG Projects, The SEALang Library, 2009, sealang.net/mk/katuic.htm.
- Source 2: Sidwell, Paul, and Kees Jan Bos. “Kui Ntua.” *The Handbook of Austroasiatic Languages (2 Vols)*, edited by Mathias Jenny and Paul Sidwell, Brill, 2015, pp. 837–880.
- Source 1: Diffloth, Gerard. *Kuay in Cambodia: A Vocabulary with Historical Comments*. UNESCO, 2011, unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0021/002174/217422E.pdf.
- Source 2: Jacques, Claude. “The Historical Development of Khmer Culture from the Death of Suryavarman II to the Late 16th Century.” *Bayon: New Perspectives*, edited by Joyce Clark, River Books,

2007, pp. 28-49.

- Source 3: Baird, Ian G. "Indigenous Peoples' and Land: Comparing Communal Land Titling and Its Implications in Cambodia and Laos." *Asia Pacific Viewpoint*, vol. 54, no. 3, 2013, pp. 269-281.
- Source 1: Asia Indigenous Peoples Pact. *Indigenous Women in Southeast Asia: Challenges in Their Access to Justice*. United Nations: UN Women, 2013.
- Source 2: Pothisan, Wilart, et al. "The Social Adjustment of the Kuy People to a Multicultural Context in Southern Isan, Thailand." *Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 4, 2008, pp. 343-346., thescipub.com/PDF/jssp.2008.343.346.pdf.
- Source 1: Kuoy, B. "Ethics and Cambodian Worldviews on Nature." *Ethics in Science and Environmental Politics*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2013, pp. 49-57, www.int-res.com/articles/ese2013/13/e013p049.pdf.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0021/002174/217422E.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Diffloth, Gerard. *Kuay in Cambodia: A Vocabulary with Historical Comments*. UNESCO, 2011
- Source 2 URL: www.sil.org/resources/archives/9014
- Source 2 Description: Mann, Noel, and Linda Markowski. "A Rapid Appraisal of Kuy Dialects Spoken in Cambodia." *SIL Electronic Reports* 2005-018.
- Source 3 URL: www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/spirits-forest-cambodias-kuy-people-practice-spirit-based.
- Source 3 Description: Keating, Neal. "Spirits of the Forest: Cambodia's Kuy People Practice Spirit-Based Conservation." *Cultural Survival*, 2012, www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/spirits-forest-cambodias-kuy-people-practice-spirit-based.
- Source 1 URL: thescipub.com/PDF/jssp.2008.343.346.pdf.
- Source 1 Description: Pothisan, Wilart, et al. "The Social Adjustment of the Kuy People to a Multicultural Context in Southern Isan, Thailand." *Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 4, 2008, pp. 343-346., thescipub.com/PDF/jssp.2008.343.346.pdf.
- Source 1 URL: https://s3.amazonaws.com/berkeley-center/CambodiaIndigenousReport_Final.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011
- Source 1 URL: www.int-res.com/articles/ese2013/13/e013p049.pdf.
- Source 1 Description: Kuoy, B. "Ethics and Cambodian Worldviews on Nature." *Ethics in Science and Environmental Politics*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2013, pp. 49-57, www.int-res.com/articles/ese2013/13/e013p049.pdf.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: http://www.siamese-heritage.org/jsspdf/1951/JSS_039_2c_Seidenfaden_KuiPeopleOfCambodiaAndSiam.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Seidenfaden, Erik. "The Kui People of Cambodia and Siam." *Journal of the Siam Society*, vol. 39, no. 2, Jan. 1952, pp. 144-180.
- Source 2 URL: sealang.net/mk/katuic.htm.

–Source 2 Description: “The Katuic Branch.” SEALANG Projects, The SEALang Library, 2009, sealang.net/mk/katuic.htm.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

|

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 400000

Notes: (Paul Sidwell and Kees Jan Bos, 2015. p. 837)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (trying to be organized-controlled by larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are Village leaders within the Kuy culture in Cambodia. (see Adams, Nathaniel. Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming. World Faiths Development, 2011 p.16)

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: In the Cambodian context, women are often spiritual leaders, while men are village leaders. See Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p.42.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: It has been suggested that the Kuy played an important role in iron smelting for the Angkor empire (Groslier, 1973). The relationship that the Kuy had with the monument of Angkor is currently unknown.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Keating, Neal. “Spirits of the Forest: Cambodia's Kuy People Practice Spirit-Based Conservation.” Cultural Survival, 2012, www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/spirits-forest-

cambodias-kuy-people-practice-spirit-based.

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: "A community's burial forest is generally of a more uniform size, ranging from one to five hectares. Particularly in the northeast of the country, cremated remains are interred in a community's burial forest either in large jars or specially constructed burial houses." (Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p.21)

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: There is an overlap between Buddhism and Animistic practices for the Kuy. They continue to respect and patron ancient monuments throughout their regions.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Spirit houses are small constructions found outside of homes and are places to provide offerings to local spirits. Incense, fruits and sometimes alcohol are common offerings within spirit houses.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Shines for local spirits that reside in the forests, mountains and near villages. Some spirit names include Ah'ret, Neak Ta, or Phi

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Shrines and Ceremonial stones. Keating, Neal B. "Kuy Alterities: The Struggle to Conceptualise and Claim Indigenous Land Rights in Neoliberal Cambodia." *Asia Pacific Viewpoint*, vol. 54, no. 3, 2013, pp. 309–322. ---. "Spirits of the Forest: Cambodia's Kuy People Practice Spirit-Based Conservation."

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to ecological features:

– Yes

Notes: Water is significant, as well as forests themselves. "Water resources such as springs, lakes and streams can have special spiritual significance and are often integrated into spirit forest areas." (see Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p. 21)

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The forests are spaces for religious offerings, worship to appease spirits, and burials. "Indigenous communities generally have between two and five spirit forests of varying size, as well as one community burial forest. These spiritually significant forest areas may be shared among several communities. The size of each individual spirit forest is dictated, in part, by the physical geography of the land itself, with landscape features such as mountains, streams, or rocks acting as natural boundaries or reference points; the actual area is typically only roughly defined. Because spirit forests are often partially based on physical features, their size can vary greatly, ranging from a half-hectare islet to an entire mountaintop of over 200 hectares." (Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p. 21)

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

- Yes [specify]: spirits are connected with the forest and nature
- Yes [specify]: spirits are connected with the forest and nature

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
- Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

- ↳ In a human form:
- Yes

- ↳ In animal/plant form:
- Yes

- ↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
- Yes

Notes: In Cambodia, many Kuy are also Buddhist. Buddhists believe that a person is continually reborn, in a human or non-human form, which is dependent upon his or her actions in a previous life.

- ↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
- Yes

- ↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
- Yes

- ↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:
- Yes [specify]: In Cambodia, many Kuy are also Buddhist. Buddhists believe that a person is continually reborn, in a human or non-human form, which is dependent upon his or her actions in a previous life.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The Kuy in Cambodia hold rituals and prepare burials for their dead in designated burial forests. Many of these traditional forests have been compromised by development projects in Cambodia, especially in the last 15 years. (see The Rights of Indigenous People in Cambodia. Indigenous Peoples NGO Network (IPNN), 2010, The Rights of Indigenous People in Cambodia.)

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: In Cambodia, they cremate and inter the dead. "Particularly in the northeast of the country, cremated remains are interred in a community's burial forest either in large jars or specially constructed burial houses." (see Adams , Nathaniel. Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p.21)

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Secondary burial:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Bodies are brought into a burial forest where the land is selected and appropriate rituals are conducted. Internment and cremation are practiced.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Both Cremation (with the use of jars following) and Internment are practiced.

Notes: There is little research done on this, but recent archaeological work on the Iron Age in

Cambodia and Northeast Thailand may be linked to early Kuy culture. This research needs to be done. See: Higham, C F W. "The Iron Age of the Mun Valley, Thailand." *The Antiquaries Journal* 91.1 (2011): 101-144. Nojima, Yoko. "Non-Ceramic Grave Goods of Phum Snay in the Context of Sociopolitical Development in Northwest Cambodia." *Water Civilization* (2013):161-180. Boyd, W.E., Higham, C.F.W., & McGrath, R.J. et al. (1999). *The Geoarchaeology of the Iron Age Ditched Sites of the Upper Mae Nam Mun Valley, N.E. Thailand I: Palaeodrainage, Site-Landscape Relationships and the Origins of the Moats.* *Geoarchaeology: An International Journal*, 14, 675-716.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Keating notes that, "besides cyclical ceremonies of supplication and thanksgiving, Ahrets are consulted and prayed to in the event of sickness or in the need to divine the future. (Keating, Neal B. "From Spirit Forest to Rubber Plantation: The Accelerating Disaster of 'Development' in Cambodia." *ASIANetwork Exchange: A Journal for Asian Studies in the Liberal Arts*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2012, p. 68-74)
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Keating notes that Cambodian Kuy spirits, including Ahrets, are known to experience emotion and respond reciprocally to the behaviour of others around them, including living people..."yet they are more powerful than living people, and thus also dangerous". (Keating, Neal B. "From Spirit Forest to Rubber Plantation: The Accelerating Disaster of 'Development' in Cambodia." *ASIANetwork Exchange: A Journal for Asian Studies in the Liberal Arts*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2012, p. 68-74)

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: through the environment as they are within the environment

Notes: Keating writes, "During my fieldwork, my Kuy interlocutors repeatedly informed me that land equals life, that the forests and the mountains are places where Ahrets reside, and that the destruction of the forests is making the Ahrets very angry, in addition to taking away people's source of livelihood." (Keating, Neal B. "From Spirit Forest to Rubber Plantation: The Accelerating Disaster of 'Development' in Cambodia." *ASIANetwork Exchange: A Journal for Asian Studies in the Liberal Arts*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2012, p. 68-74)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: There are recurring patterns of spiritual geography among the Kuy. Primary among these are beliefs in a variety of local spirits that reside in the forests, mountains and near the villages. These spirits have different names, such as Ah'ret, Neak Ta, or Phi. Keating, Neal B. "Spirits of the Forest: Cambodia's Kuy People Practice Spirit-Based Conservation." *Cultural Survival*, 2012, www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/spirits-forest-cambodias-kuy-people-practice-spirit-based.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They are powerful; more powerful than humans.
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: through the environment

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Keating notes that, "there are observably recurring cognized patterns that some Kuy share with other Indigenous peoples in Cambodia, which include honouring the existence of powerful local spirits. These are known as Ahret, Neak Ta, or Phi. These spirits are related to past ancestors who are thought to linger in the forests. They "retain a kind of personhood and hold acquired mystical power over health and illness". (Keating, Neal B. "From Spirit Forest to Rubber Plantation: The Accelerating Disaster of 'Development' in Cambodia." *ASIANetwork Exchange: A Journal for Asian Studies in the Liberal Arts*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2012, p. 68-74)

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
 - Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Yes

- ↳ Food:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Sacred space(s):
 - Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: They care about the behaviour of the living

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Morals

Notes: Keating notes that Cambodian Kuy view their Ahrets as having a moral aspect, and that they judge and act upon the behavior of people. "When the people behave well, the Ahrets contribute to their well-being. This judgement extends not only to interpersonal relations, but also to what we might call internature relations—the relations between people and the natural environment around them". (Keating, Neal B. "From Spirit Forest to Rubber Plantation: The Accelerating Disaster of 'Development' in Cambodia." *ASIANetwork Exchange: A Journal for Asian Studies in the Liberal Arts*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2012, p. 68-74)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes

- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes

- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes

- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes

- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes

- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes

- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Reverence to the spirits

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Because many Kuy are Buddhist, there are requirements for sexual abstinence.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Because many Kuy are Buddhism, there are requirements for sexual abstinence.

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - Yes
- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other sexual constraints (females):
 - Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Because many Kuy are Buddhist, there are dietary restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Tattoos have been used as a cultural marker, as well as enlarging earlobes.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: According to Seidenfaden, the Kuy in Thailand practised "black-magic," which could be a European generalization for something that was little understood at the time. (see Seidenfaden, Erik. "The Kui People of Cambodia and Siam." p. 163)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: There are village leaders (generally men) and spiritual caretakers (generally women). See Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: There are sacrifices that are continually repeated with the seasons, including farming sacrifices. (see Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p. 16).

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Kuy in Cambodia practice Animism and Buddhism, they often engage with alcohol.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: They often have their ears pierced, wear jewellery and occasionally apply tattoos.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

↳ Circumcision:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there are some cultural taboos, including food. (see Adams, Nathaniel. *Indigenous Spirituality in Cambodia: Implications for Development Programming*. World Faiths Development Dialogue Reports, 2011, p.22)

↳ Hair:

– Field doesn't know

Dress:

– Field doesn't know

Ornaments:

– Yes

Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Other:

– Yes [specify]: It is important to note that the Kuy are diverse and their cultural practices vary. Also, among the existing regions where there are Kuy populations, many prefer not to identify as an indigenous group to avoid conflict with development projects. Considering these factors, and the effects of globalization, many traditional cultural markers have been compromised. (see Baird, Ian G. "Indigenous Peoples' and Land: Comparing Communal Land Titling and Its Implications in Cambodia and Laos." *Asia Pacific Viewpoint*, vol. 54, no. 3, 2013, pp. 269-281. ---. "The Construction of 'Indigenous Peoples' in Cambodia." *Alterities in Asia: Reflections on Identity and Regionalism*, London: Routledge, 2011, pp. 155-176).

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Kinship terminology is applied. (see Diffloth, Gerard. *Kuay in Cambodia: A Vocabulary with Historical Comments*. UNESCO, 2011, unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0021/002174/217422E.pdf. p.98)

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Field doesn't know

Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Field doesn't know

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a village leader, and also a spiritual leader within most Kuy groups in Cambodia.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: This is not a formal calendar in the traditional sense, but they have their own concept of time, and seasonal change, which is utilized for rituals, and sacrifice.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Today the Kuy people often obtain food from town areas because of migration, or when they are unable to produce their own food, due to land grabs, and forced displacement.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)